

CHALLENGES IN LEARNING LATIN LANGUAGE.

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Abstract: Students study Latin at medical institutes. Many of them face various problems when learning Latin. This presentation reveals the problems faced by students and their solutions.

Key words: difficulties, grammar, names of plants, solutions.

The problem of the research: many students, studying the Latin names of medicinal plants and its grammar, do not even suspect what difficulties may hinder their path and how they can be overcome.

The relevance of the topic: nothing happens without a solution, as well as difficulties in learning Latin faced by students of medical universities. Knowing these solutions helps you learn this language more deeply and use them effectively in the future. This is what indicates the relevance of the topic.

The results of the study:

- **The origin of Latin language:**

Latin is an Italic language which originated in the Italian peninsula, and was originally spoken in Latium and Ancient Rome located along the Mediterranean Sea.

- **Areas of learning Latin language.**

The study of the Latin language course pursues a purely professional goal - to prepare a terminologically competent doctor. Learning words is one of the most important components of the Latin language classes. It is Latin vocabulary that will help in further work with medical terminology. In addition to medical terminology, the classes also pay attention to Latin aphorisms, the knowledge of which helps students not only learn centuries-old wisdom, but also better memorize Latin words.

- **Problems in studying Latin.**

Appropriate solutions for these problems.

Literatures

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